

REPORT:

A1.3.1: Investigation on the State-of-the-art of available methodologies for flow control (nano/micro/meso/macro fluidics)

Work package 1

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This report was written as part of activity A3.2.1 from the EMPIR Establishing Metrology Standards in Microfluidic Devices (MFMET) project. The three-year European project commenced on 1st June 2021 and focused on providing a generic methodology of accurate measurement of a particular quantity in a microfluidic device by utilising standardised methods and reference documents, e.g. VIM & GUM. For more details about this project, please visit <https://mfmet.eu>

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1. Scope

This document provides the investigation on the State-of-the-art of available methodologies for flow control (nano/micro/meso/macro fluidics).

Activity number	Activity description	Partners (Lead in bold)
A1.3.1 M21	Investigation on the State-of-the-art of available methodologies for flow control (nano/micro/meso/macro fluidics).	HS , INESC MN, IPQ, NEL, UG, CMI

2. Definitions, Vocabulary and Metrological terms

Definitions concerning the topic flow control can be found in report **A1.1.2: Definitions, Symbols and Vocabulary of Flow Control**.

Metrological terms can be found in MFMET **A2.1.1 Report on Metrology Methodology** and in **The International Vocabulary of Metrology – VIM**.

3. Normative References

ISO/IEC Guide 99:2007 - International Vocabulary of Metrology – Basic and General Concepts and Associated Terms (VIM 3 rd edition) or JCGM 200:2012, BIPM

ISO/IEC Guide 98-3 - Evaluation of measurement data – Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurement (GUM) or JCGM 100:2008, BIPM The International System of Units (SI), 8th edition, 2006, updated in 2014, BIPM.

ISO/IEC Guide 98-4:2012 - Evaluation of measurement data – The role of measurement uncertainty in conformity assessment or JCGM 106:2012, BIPM ISO 80000:2006 - Quantities and units

ISO, ISO/DIS 10991 Microfluidics —Vocabulary; ISO: Geneve, Switzerland (<https://www.iso.org/standard/82146.html>)

ISO 80000:2006 - Quantities and Units, ISO, International Electrotechnical Commission, IEC; ISO: Geneve, Switzerland, 2020; Parts 1-13

4. Definitions and Flow rate segments

4.1 Definition nano/micro/meso/macro fluidics

Nanofluidics:

Nanofluidics is the study and application of fluids in and around geometries with nanoscale characteristic dimensions (1-100 nm). (Xu, Yan. "Nanofluidics: a new arena for materials science." *Advanced Materials* 30.3 (2018): 1702419.) It involves the dynamics of fluids confined in nanoscale structures¹. Nanofluids are the conventional heat transfer fluids containing solid nanoparticles (https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-981-33-4248-4_2).

Microfluidics:

“What is microfluidics? It is the science and technology of systems that process or manipulate small (10⁻⁹ to 10⁻¹⁸ litres) amounts of fluids, using channels with dimensions of tens to hundreds of micrometres.” Whitesides, G. The origins and the future of microfluidics. Nature 442, 368–373 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature05058>

Cheriyedath (2019) defines it as “the study of systems that can process small quantities of fluids by using tiny channels having dimensions at the microscale – typically tens to hundreds of micrometres.” Cheriyedath, S. (2019). What is Microfluidics? <https://www.news-medical.net/life-sciences/What-is-Microfluidics.aspx>

Nguyen, Wereley, and Shaegh (2019) define it as “the science and engineering of systems in which fluid behavior differs from conventional flow theory primarily due to the small length scale of the system.” Nguyen, N.-T., Wereley, S. T., and Shaegh, S. A. M. (2019). Fundamentals and applications of microfluidics. Artech house.

Mesofluidics

Mesofluidics is rarely used in the literature. Here are two definitions: 1) Mesofluidics involves the application of millimeter- to centimeter-sized hydraulics to problems that require substantial amounts of power to be generated and applied in a limited space 4.

2) Mesofluidic refers to the systems or devices that leverage microfluidic principles (e.g., numbering up instead of scaling up) but operate at industrial scale flowrates (e.g., gallons per hour in contrast to milliliters per hour). <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cep.2022.108795>

Millifluidics

Millifluidics is a field of research that focuses on the study of fluid flow and behavior in microchannels with characteristic dimensions ranging from hundreds of micrometers to a few millimeters. It is an intermediate scale between microfluidics and macrofluidics, where the channels are smaller than those typically studied in macrofluidics but larger than those in microfluidics.

Source: <https://www.intechopen.com/chapters/61556>

Source: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2588842021000286>

Macrofluidics

While there isn't a widely accepted definition for macrofluidics, it can be inferred from the definitions of micro and mesofluidics that macrofluidics would involve the study and manipulation of fluids at a larger, macroscopic scale. This would include the everyday fluid systems we are familiar with, such as plumbing systems, rivers, and weather systems. We define Macrofluidics as a field of research that focuses on the study of fluid flow and behavior in channels with cm dimensions and with flow rates in the l/min range.

4.1 Flow rate regimes

There are different definitions available for flow regimes. You can divide them in 3 categories like Low, Middle or high as defined here:

1. Low flow rate: 1 nL/min to 1 μ L/min -> calibration by optical methods preferably, or low-flow volumetric methods in general. National metrology standards (best calibration uncertainty) would be around 2% in general.
2. Middle flow rate: 1 μ L/min to 100 μ L/min (hot spot) -> calibration by gravimetric or volumetric methods, national metrology standards (best calibration uncertainty) would be around 0.5% in general.
3. High flow rate: 100 μ L/min to 10 mL/min -> calibration by gravimetric methods, national metrology standards (best calibration uncertainty) would be around 0.1% in general.

A section option is to define it into micro, nano, and milliliter flow regimes. Flow rate is the amount of fluid that passes through a system or a channel per unit time. The different ranges of flow rate can be categorized as follows:

1. **Microliter (μ L) Flow Regime/ Microflow:** This regime typically falls under the domain of microfluidics. Microflow refers to flow rates in the range of microliters per minute (μ L/min) to nanoliters per minute (nL/min). Microflow is typically studied in microfluidics, which deals with fluid behavior in channels with dimensions on the micrometer scale. The flow can be either laminar or turbulent ¹. Laminar flow is characterized by smooth or in regular paths of particles of the fluid, while turbulent flow

is characterized by the irregular movement of particles of the fluid [1](#). The flow regime can also be classified according to the geometry of a conduit or flow area [1](#).

2. **Nanoliter (nl) Flow Regime:** This regime is typically associated with nanofluidics. An increasing number of micro- and nano-fluidic applications require the control of fluid flows in the nanoliter per minute regime [2](#). These include drug infusion, nano-electrospray ionization (nanoESI), and high pressure liquid chromatography (HPLC), among others [2](#). The ultimate performance of flow-based measurements in microfluidic systems is limited by their accuracy at the nanoliter-per-minute scale [3](#).
3. **Milliliter (ml) Flow Regime/ Milliflow:** This regime is typically associated with mesofluidics and macrofluidics. Milliflow refers to flow rates in the range of milliliters per minute (mL/min) to microliters per minute ($\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$). Milliflow is studied in millifluidics, which deals with fluid behavior in channels with dimensions on the millimeter scale. The flow can be either laminar or turbulent [1](#). Laminar flow is characterized by smooth or in regular paths of particles of the fluid, while turbulent flow is characterized by the irregular movement of particles of the fluid [1](#). The flow regime can also be classified according to the geometry of a conduit or flow area.
4. **Macroflow:** Macroflow refers to flow rates in the range of liters per minute (L/min) to milliliters per minute (mL/min). Macroflow is studied in macrofluidics, which deals with fluid behavior in systems with dimensions much larger than those studied in microfluidics or millifluidics.

Overall, the range of flow rate depends on the specific application and the scale of the system being studied or used. Please note that as the scale decreases from milliliter to nanoliter, the dominant forces and effects can change, leading to different behaviors and applications at each scale

5. Literature concerning flow control

Flow control in general is a subfield of fluid dynamics. Basically, it means that by making small changes to the configuration, large engineering benefits can be achieved, such as a reduction in drag, an increase in lift, an improvement in mixing, or a reduction in noise.

Flow control is a broad field. There are two categories for each type of control: passive and active. Passive forms of flow control, in which no energy is added to the system, are common. For example, cars are optimized to reduce drag.

Active flow control is at the intersection of fluid mechanics and control theory. Through flow control, for example one could increase vehicle efficiency, reduce carbon dioxide emissions, and lower operating costs, which would mitigate future increases in oil and gas prices.

There are many books and papers published dealing with the topic methodology for flow control. Most of these references divided flow control techniques into active flow control (AFC) and passive control:

Abbildung 1: Methodology for flow control [Source: Wang, J., & Feng, L. (2018). Introduction. In *Flow Control Techniques and Applications* (Cambridge Aerospace Series, pp. 1-22). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. doi:10.1017/9781316676448.002]

Source:

- Gad-el-Hak, Mohamad. "Flow control." (1989): 261-293.
- Kral, Linda D. "Active flow control technology." *ASME Fluids Engineering Technical Brief* (2000): 1-28.
- Ashill, P., Fulker, J., & Hackett, K. (2005). A review of recent developments in flow control. *The Aeronautical Journal*, 109(1095), 205-232. doi:10.1017/S0001924000005200

The term "flow control" is mostly used in the field of aerodynamics. In this report we focus on flow control for nano/micro/meso-fluidics.

5.1 Flow Control in Microfluidics:

Microfluidics is a growing field for example in life science that deals with the control of small amounts of liquid. In this report, we will discuss state-of-the-art of the methodology of flow control for microfluidic devices, and how precision pressure regulators can be used to achieve optimal results.

Flow control is a critical aspect of micro and nanofluidics, which is the study of fluid behavior and transport in channels and structures with dimensions on the order of micrometers or nanometers. There are several methodologies available for flow control in micro and nanofluidics, and the state-of-the-art of these methodologies can be categorized into three main groups: passive, active, and feedback control.

Passive Flow Control:

Passive flow control methods rely on the geometry and surface properties of the microfluidic channel to control the flow. The most common passive flow control techniques are based on the use of microstructures, such as pillars, grooves, and channels, that induce turbulence or redirect the flow to achieve the desired behavior. Other passive methods include the use of hydrophobic/hydrophilic surfaces, porous materials, and microfilters to control fluid flow.

Active Flow Control:

Active flow control methods involve the use of external forces or stimuli to manipulate the fluid flow. These methods typically rely on the use of microactuators, such as electrokinetic pumps, piezoelectric actuators, and microvalves, to control the fluid flow. External fields, such as electric, magnetic, and acoustic fields, can also be used to control the fluid flow in micro and nanochannels.

Feedback Flow Control:

Feedback flow control methods involve the use of sensors and control systems to monitor and adjust the fluid flow in real-time. These methods typically rely on the use of microsensors, such as pressure and flow sensors, to measure the fluid behavior, and feedback control systems, such as proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controllers, to adjust the external stimuli and maintain the desired flow behavior.

Recent advances in micro and nanofabrication technologies have enabled the development of new and innovative flow control methods. For example, the use of 3D printing and soft lithography techniques has allowed the fabrication of complex microfluidic channels and structures with high precision and resolution. Furthermore, the integration of microsensors and microcontrollers has enabled the development of closed-loop feedback control systems that can maintain the fluid flow with high accuracy and stability.

In summary, the state-of-the-art of flow control in micro and nanofluidics involves a combination of passive, active, and feedback control methods, and the recent advances in microfabrication and sensing technologies have enabled the development of new and innovative flow control techniques.

5.1 Guidelines and protocols on flow control

Micro and nano-flow rate primary measurement methods are described in the first deliverable of the “Metrology for Drug Delivery II” project, available at https://drugmetrology.com/wp-content/uploads/2020/10/MeDDII-D1_V1-1.pdf

This report includes the description of the following methods and their associated uncertainty budgets:

- Gravimetric method
- Optical method: meniscus tracking
- Optical method: pendant drop
- MicroPIV/MicroPTV
- Displacement method

These methods are intended to be used when the best accuracy in flow measurement is needed, or in case of a flow meter or flow generator calibration but the most used method for microflow determination is the gravimetric method.

More information can also be found in the MFMET report *A2.2.1: A literature review of existing metrology and normative standards related to the flow properties and microfluidic devices*.

5.2 Review papers on flow control

There are several papers that describe method for measuring flow, namely:

- E. Batista, N. Almeida, I. Godinho and E. Filipe, “Uncertainty Calculation in Gravimetric Microflow Measurements”, *Advanced Mathematical and Computational Tools in Metrology and Testing X*, pp. 98-104, 2015

- Hugo Bissig, Harm Tido Petter, Peter Lucas, Elsa Batista, Eduarda Filipe, Nelson Almeida, Luis Filipe Ribeiro, João Gala, Rui Martins, Benoit Savanier, Florestan Ogheard, Anders Koustrup Niemann, Joost Lötters and Wouter Sparreboom “Primary standards for measuring flow rates from 100 nl/min to 1 ml/min – gravimetric principle”, Biomedical Engineering, 60(4), 301-316, 2015
- Franco Marinozzi, Fabiano Bini and Paolo Cappa, “Calibrator for microflow delivery systems”, Review of Scientific Instruments 76, 015106, 2005
- Andrea Cioncolini, Fabio Scenini, Jonathan Duff, “Micro-orifice single-phase liquid flow: Pressure drop measurements and prediction”, Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science, Volume 65, pages 33-40, 2015
- B. Akselli and I. Teke, “Experimentally investigation of the CCD binning option in particle imaging velocimetry measurements of laminar flows”, Int. J. Metrol. Qual. Eng. 2, 83–89, 2011
- E. Batista, et al., (2020), "Development of an experimental setup for microflow measurement using interferometry", Flow Measurement and Instrumentation, 75, 101789
- Ogheard F, Cassette P, Boudaoud AW. Development of an optical measurement method for “sampled” micro-volumes and nanoflow rates. Flow Meas Instrum 2020;73:101746

5.3 Commercially available flow control

Flow rate control is critical for most microfluidic applications and is usually accomplished by external flow generators connected to the microfluidic chip. Four are the most common types used:

- Peristaltic pumps
- Syringe pumps
- Pressure driven flow generator
- Piezo electric pumps

A data base of all the manufacturers and pumps specifications can be found in <https://mfmet.eu/publications/> .(DTI is developing such data base).

The database can be accessed (and to use it, one must create a user) at the following webpage: <https://yoda.teknologisk.dk/MFMET-database/>

There is a guide for how to use the database on our MFMET teams folder: <https://zenodo.org/records/8336435>